

Investigation of the role of JunD on defending Ferroptosis in Cycling Hypoxia of Glioblastoma

1. Abstract

JunD, a member of the activated protein-1 family of transcription factors, is known as a distinct protector for ischemia/reperfusion-induced injury in the liver or brain via anti-oxidative stress. However, the role of JunD in glioblastoma is obscure. Recently, our preliminary results demonstrated that cycling hypoxia, a specific type of tumour microenvironment (TME) differing from chronic hypoxia, was able to induce JunD activation in glioblastoma cells. Interestingly, knockdown of JunD in glioblastoma cells exhibited a decrease in cell viability under cycling hypoxia. Moreover, the treatments of ferroptosis inhibitors could restore these effects, suggesting JunD as a novel transcription factor involved in anti-ferroptosis under cycling hypoxia. Gene correlation analysis from clinical RNA-seq datasets in glioblastoma showed that GPX4 was most significantly associated with JunD compared to other anti-ferroptosis regulators. Bioinformatics analysis also identified two JunD binding sites in the human GPX4 promoter sequence from bases -2000 to +100. Based on these findings, we hypothesize that JunD promotes anti-ferroptosis through upregulation of GPX4 under cycling hypoxia in glioblastoma. In this project, we aim to investigate the roles and mechanisms of JunD on cycling hypoxia-regulated ferroptosis in glioblastoma. To achieve this goal, we will first observe the effect of cycling hypoxia on the regulation of JunD via immunofluorescence and flow cytometry assays. Second, we will determine the role of JunD in cycling hypoxia-regulated ferroptosis via the genetic manipulation of JunD together with in vitro studies. Finally, we will investigate the molecular mechanisms of JunD-regulated GPX4 in glioblastoma via molecular studies. The results derived from this project can not only address the roles and mechanisms of JunD in the regulation of ferroptosis in glioblastoma but also provide a novel therapeutic target against TME-mediated anti-ferroptosis.

2. Motive and Focus of Proposed Research

Glioblastoma Multiforme (GBM) represents one of the most fatal and refractory solid tumours in the adult central nervous system. Despite its relatively low incidence rate (3.23 per 100,000 population), GBM is the most common malignant brain tumour and has an abysmal prognosis with a five-year survival rate of only 6.8% in the United States.¹ Ever since the seminal phase III trial in 2005 in which Stupp et al. consolidated the use of radiotherapy plus concomitant and adjuvant temozolomide (TMZ) after complete surgical resection,² no other therapeutic intervention has significantly altered this mainstay of confronting GBM.

Part of the reasons behind this sluggish therapeutic advancement of GBM is its hostile intrinsic nature, which features genetic heterogeneity, infiltrative propensity, metabolic reprogramming, and renewable capability stemming from glioblastoma stem cells (GSCs).³ These intrinsic factors allow glioblastoma cells to evade immune responses and to survive therapeutic interventions while moving on to expand their territory by adapting to and reshaping the surrounding tumour microenvironment (TME). For instance, upon the threat of alkylating agents such as TMZ, around 60% of patients with unmethylated MGMT promoter (ranging from 53.4% to 67.9% depending on different clinical trials) dodge the attack from the TMZ-induced DNA double-stranded break by reversing this damage with functional MGMT instead of futile DNA mismatch repair.⁴ TMZ-resistant glioblastoma cells also enhance their cell division and anti-apoptosis ability by upregulating the signalling pathway of NRAS/MEK/ERK through the sponging effect between a circular RNA, CircASAP1, and a microRNA, MiR-502-5p. This RNA interaction frees up NRAS from being inhibited by MiR-502-5p.⁵ Apart from the above mentioned transcriptional and post-transcriptional modifications, post-translational mechanisms such as histone deacetylases (HDAC), specifically HDAC 1/2/6, enable glioblastoma cells to overcome TMZ-induced chemotoxicity by activating specificity protein 1 (sp1), which then evokes downstream pathways that promote anti-oxidative gene expression and tumour cell stemness.⁶ The intrinsic nature of TMZ-resistant GBM can further transmit lncRNA, fusion gene, and microRNA by exosome to alter the characteristics of nearby immune⁷, glia⁸, and glioblastoma cells⁹ toward a more tumorigenic state. In addition to TMZ-induced resistance, the inherent plasticity of glioblastoma cells covers the spectrum of therapy resistance induced by immunotherapy¹⁰ and to a lesser extent, radiotherapy¹¹, substantiating the current stalemate of the glioblastoma clinical trials.

On the other hand, the hostile extrinsic nature of GBM is mainly the aftermath of interplays between glioblastoma cells and their TME. Spatially, TME of GBM encompasses central necrotic zone, peripheral dysregulated vasculature, and intermediate hypoxic region, which together offers a dynamic place that sustains stresses and incubates glioblastoma progression.¹² Dispersing throughout this environment are cellular players, largely consisting of immune cells, astrocytes, neurons, and endothelial cells, which synergistically act as recipients of tumour influence as well as instigators of malignant transformation.¹³ Among these spatial features and cellular players, cycling hypoxia garners recent interest due to its unique characteristics of nurturing angiogenesis, therapy resistance, pro-tumoural inflammation, and metastasis.¹⁴ Cycling hypoxia originates when a solid tumour outgrows its blood supplies, creating a central necrotic and chronic hypoxic zone while expanding into a perfusion-limited intermittent hypoxic region surrounded by poorly-growth vasculature.¹² In comparison with chronic hypoxia, cycling hypoxia possesses an additional temporal aspect in regards to its reoxygenation cycle. These inflows of blood after temporary hypoxic periods generate specific features, predominantly reactivation of ATP-driven mechanism¹⁵ and reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, aiding cells to reprogram signalling pathways in recovery from hypoxic shocks. Although chronic hypoxia also generates elevated ROS levels derived from mitochondrial complex III in the electron transport chain,¹⁶ cycling hypoxia levels up ROS with available oxygen molecules by activating oxidoreductases such as xanthine oxidase, NADPH oxidase (NOX), and cytochrome p450.¹⁷ This surge of ROS in cycling hypoxia initiates a more robust activation of HIF-1 α and NF- κ B, which upregulate genes expression related to pro-tumoural inflammation, angiogenesis, and attracting regulatory immunocytes.¹⁸ Moreover, in the context of GBM, the group of Hsieh et al. have reported that ROS-related regulatory mechanisms including NOX4, Bcl-x1, and ABCB1 can induce radioresistance¹⁹, chemoresistance^{20,21}, and tumour invasion plus infiltration²² under cycling hypoxia. Ultimately, excessive ROS generated by cycling hypoxic tumour cells confers worsened condition to GBM's TME and subsequent promotion of GBM progression.

Yet, how glioblastoma cells survive under this higher oxidative stress in cycling hypoxia requires further elucidation. Generally, cancer cells directly counter higher ROS levels by modifying their sulphur metabolism, NADPH production, and activating the antioxidant defence system.²³ In other types of cancer cell lines, Rouschop et al. suggested that autophagy is required to lessen the ROS generated from cycling hypoxia,²⁴ which could result from the PERK-mediated cellular defence system.²⁵ A preprint from Sun et al. reveals an interesting finding that PI3K/AKT/HIF-1 α upregulates the expression of GPX4, a crucial anti-ferroptosis protein, under hypoxic condition and prevents ferroptosis in GBM.²⁶ Combining previous research showing upregulation of PI3K/AKT/HIF-1 α in endothelial cells under cycling hypoxia,²⁷ the HIF-1 α /GPX4 can well be an axis that lower cycling hypoxic ROS in GBM. Nevertheless, given its tumourigenic inclination and vast territory (spanning between 29 – 62% of tumour area in comparison to 23 to 54% of chronic hypoxia)¹⁸, cycling hypoxia is still a relevant target for countering the progression of GBM. Dissecting GBM's strategies of sustaining higher ROS in cycling hypoxia can illuminate future therapeutic approaches. Therefore, we proposed a novel hypothesis that JunD can defend ferroptosis in cycling hypoxic GBM by activating GPX4. Detailed literature review and preliminary data will be rigorously discussed in the next section.

3. Literature Review and Discussion

JunD: a cell death modulator that potentially guards ferroptosis in cycling hypoxia

JunD is a JUN-related transcription factor that contains a basic leucine-zipper dimerization motif. JUN along with FOS, ATF, and MAF family are components of AP-1, a dimerized transcription factor that is tumourigenic or tumour-suppressive depending on its activating targets.²⁸ The main regulatory mechanisms of JunD is on the post-translational level, including cytoplasmic activation by mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), such as extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERKs) and c-JUN N-terminal kinases (JNKs), as well as nuclear inhibition by Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN1).²⁹ But dimerized JunD including JunD-FOS, JunD-MEN1, and JunD-JunD can also transcriptionally activate or repress the JunD gene expression through the binding on TPA response element (TRE) within the promoter region of JunD.²⁹ JunD is generally regarded as a cell protector by activating or repressing genes related to anti-apoptosis^{30,31} and anti-oxidative stress^{32,33}. However, the role of JunD in regulating ferroptosis under cycling hypoxia has not been intricately discussed, despite several research hinting at this possibility. Cycling hypoxia may regulate JunD function via post-translational and transcriptional mechanisms. Although both chronic

hypoxia³⁴ and cycling hypoxia²² upregulate the activity of ERKs and JNKs, chronic hypoxia lessens the amount of phosphorylated JunD in lung tissues,³⁴ while the effect of cycling hypoxia on the JunD's activity remains unexplored. In comparison, the gene expression of JunD in peripheral red blood cells trends downward in an ischaemia-reperfusion stroke model.³⁵ However, given the importance of JunD on maintaining cell survival in ischaemia-reperfusion cells,³⁵ it is very possible that in spite of the transcriptional inhibition possibly driven by the negative feedback loop of JunD-FOS heterodimer,³⁶ the activity of JunD rather goes up through the increased function of JNKs and ERKs in glioblastoma cells.²² Regarding the links between JunD and ferroptosis, Gerald et al. have observed an accumulation of Fe³⁺ in JunD^{-/-} fibroblast, which infers the consequences of ferroptosis by overproduction of PLOOH and resulting Fenton reaction.³² Additionally, in a hepatocarcinoma model, JunD may activate ferritin heavy chain (ferritin H), an iron storage protein counteracting ferroptosis in cardiomyopathy,³⁷ by binding to its antioxidant response element.³⁸ In contrast, JunD can induce lipid accumulation in pancreatic β cells by upregulating genes associated with lipid metabolism,³⁹ which may induce ferroptosis by enriching PUFAs.⁴⁰ Overall, JunD can suppress or promote ferroptosis according to different cellular contexts. On top of the suggestions from these articles, Western blot analysis of JunD in the nuclear compartment of human GBM cell lines reveals higher JunD expression under cycling hypoxia compared to chronic hypoxia (Figure 1A), indicating that cycling hypoxia may activate JunD either transcriptionally or post-translationally. Also, genetic knockdown of JunD using shRNA reduces their cell viability, but ferroptosis inhibitors, ferrostatins and liproxstatins-1, can rescue this diminished survival rate (Figure 1C-D). This result suggests that JunD may sustain cellular features crucial in preventing ferroptosis under cycling hypoxia. Thus, strong evidence has pointed out the potential role of JunD in countering ferroptosis in GBM under cycling hypoxia.

GPX4: a nexus between ferroptosis and cycling hypoxia

Glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) is a crucial detoxifying enzyme that catalyses the reduction of phospholipid hydroperoxides (PLOOHs), which are a member of the ROS family and the main contributors to ferroptosis, a programmed cell death driven by iron-dependent phospholipid peroxidation.⁴¹ Recent research has reported several links between hypoxia and ferroptosis in cancer. Hypoxia can promote or counter ferroptosis by altering signalling pathways related to lipid and iron metabolism. On the promoting side, cancer cells that constitutively express a high level of HIFs can be prone to ferroptosis. For instance, intrinsic expression of HIF-2 α in clear cell renal cell carcinoma can enrich polyunsaturated fatty acids, a component for lipid peroxidation, and thus increase its vulnerability to ferroptosis by upregulating hypoxia-induced, lipid droplet-associated protein.⁴² By a similar pathway, a high level of HIF-2 α in colorectal cancer can drive the expression of iron and lipid regulatory genes, casting ferroptotic susceptibility to this type of cancer.⁴³ On the other hand, hypoxic cancer cells can also resist pressure from ferroptosis by upregulating protective enzymes and transcription factors. Under hypoxic treatment, mesothelioma enhances its gene expression of carbonic anhydrase IX to prevent dysregulated iron metabolism (upregulation of TFRC, IREB1/2, FPN1; downregulation of FTH/FTL) and subsequent ferroptotic and apoptotic death.⁴⁴ Considering cycling hypoxia, nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor (NRF2) has been implicated more commonly in ischaemia-reperfusion injury but also under cycling hypoxia in adenocarcinoma.⁴⁵ The transactivating targets for NRF2 are involved in preventing ferroptosis: including iron metabolism (ABCB6, BLVRA/B, FECH etc.), intermediate metabolism (AKR1B1, AKR1B10, G6PD etc.), and Glutathione synthesis (SLC7A11, GSTA, GSS etc.).⁴⁶ Nonetheless, how cycling hypoxia regulates ferroptosis through PLOOHs detoxifying system, the three major players being GPX4, ferroptosis suppressor protein 1 (FSP1)^{47,48}, and dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (DHODH)⁴⁹, requires additional clarifications. Apart from HIF-1 α ,²⁶ JunD may also be an upstream transcriptional regulator of GPX4 through the binding of its promoter region. Gene expression correlation analyses with an RNA-seq dataset in the Chinese Glioma Genome Atlas⁵⁰ reveals a higher correlation between JunD and GPX4 compared to other negative ferroptosis regulators^{51,52} in glioblastoma (Figure 2A, 2B). Their expression also correlates better in the peri-vascular region compared to other tumour regions in Ivy Glioblastoma Atlas Project spatial RNA-seq dataset⁵³ (Figure 2C). Furthermore, promoter region analysis with Eukaryotic Promoter Database⁵⁴ and ChIPSummitDB⁵⁵ have indicated potential JunD binding sites in the GPX4 promoter region (Figure 3). Therefore, JunD can also warrant as another guarding factor of ferroptosis via initiating GPX4 expression under cycling hypoxia in GBM.

4. Methods for Proposed Research

The overall objective of this study will be to explore the role and molecular mechanism of JunD in regulating ferroptosis under the cycling hypoxic microenvironment of GBM.

In view of this objective, three specific aims will be pursued:

Specific aim 1: To observe the effect of tumour cycling hypoxia on the regulation of JunD.

Specific aim 2: To determine the role of JunD in cycling hypoxia-regulated ferroptosis.

Specific aim 3: To investigate the molecular mechanisms of JunD-regulated ferroptosis.

Experimental design for specific aim 1:

First, we will transplant human GBM cell lines (U251 and GBM8401) to eight-week-old nude mice (NOD/SCID). Second, we will utilise FACS to isolate hypoxic tumour subpopulations from human GBM cell line xenografts as described in the instructor's previous studies.^{20,21} Third, we will determine JunD expression in hypoxic tumour subpopulations by co-immunostaining immunofluorescence imaging of Hoechst 33342 (perfusion marker), Pimonidazole (hypoxia marker), and JunD marker. Also, we will use Western blot analyses and qPCR to analyse the protein and gene expression from the isolated hypoxic tumour cells. Lastly, to further determine the role of cycling hypoxia in JunD regulation, we will evaluate the mRNA and protein levels of JunD with qPCR and Western blot analysis in human GBM cell lines (U251 and GBM8401) at different time points of the hypoxia-reoxygenation treatment as described in the previous protocol.^{20,21}

Experimental design for specific aim 2:

First, we will first create a JunD knockdown platform using lentivirus vectors encoding JunD shRNAs. U251 and GBM8401 glioblastoma cells will be transduced with lentivirus vectors carrying JunD shRNAs or scramble shRNAs. Second, we will determine cell viability and level of lipid peroxidation in glioblastoma with or without JunD knockdown under cycling hypoxia by MTT and lipid peroxidation colourimetric assay, respectively. Lastly, we will utilise ferroptosis inhibitors, ferrostatins and liproxstain-1, to determine whether these inhibitors can restore the ferroptotic death and alterations of lipid peroxidation level mediated by knockdown of JunD under cycling hypoxia.

Experimental design for specific aim 3:

To identify the role and molecular mechanism of JunD in the regulation of GPX4 expression, we will first transfect human GBM cell lines (U251 and GBM8401) with human JunD plasmids for overexpression of JunD and JunD siRNAs for knockdown of JunD. Then, qPCR and western blotting analysis will determine the expression of GPX4 in these cells after overexpression or knockdown of JunD. Next, to pinpoint the exact binding motifs, we will also introduce point mutations or deletions into the potential JunD binding sites of the GPX4 promoter-driven luciferase reporter gene. Lastly, we will conduct CHIP assays to confirm the binding of JunD to the GPX4 promoter.

5. Anticipated Outcomes

Specific aim 1: cycling hypoxia in GBM can activate the protein and gene expression of JunD.

Specific aim 2: JunD can prevent ferroptotic cell death under cycling hypoxia in GBM.

Specific aim 3: JunD can activate GPX4 expression by binding to its promoter.

6. Needs for Mentorship

As a student studying in medical school, it is relatively hard to obtain proper training in translational research, especially in areas around forming novel hypotheses, designing experiments, and interpreting results. Therefore, only under professor Hsieh's instructions and his expertise in the cycling hypoxia field,¹⁹⁻²² that I was able to devise this project concerning JunD function in cycling hypoxic GBM with aforethought on therapeutic applications. In the coming part of this project, Professor Hsieh's instructions are indispensable in areas such as experiment execution (Chip-seq analysis), result interpretation (IHC imaging), composing the closing report, and perhaps transforming this project into a journal article.

Figure 1. Cycling hypoxia-induced JunD activation contributes to anti-ferroptosis in glioblastoma cells. (A) Western blot analysis of nuclear JunD in U251 and GBM8401 glioblastoma cells after normoxia (N.), non-interrupted hypoxia (NIH.) and cycling hypoxia (CYH.). (B) The protein levels of JunD in U251 and GBM8401 cells lentivirally transduced with scramble (Scr.) shRNA or JunD shRNAs (C) The cell viability of U251 and GBM8401 cells with or without JunD knockdown under cycling hypoxia. Error bars, SD within triplicate experiments. *** $p < 0.001$, compared with the Scr. shRNA group. (D) The cell viability of U251 and GBM8401 cells with JunD knockdown cultured in cycling hypoxia (CYH.) in response to vehicle, ferrostatins, or liproxstatin-1 treatment. Error bars, SD within triplicate experiments. *** $p < 0.001$, compared with the non-treated group. ###, $P < 0.001$, compared with vehicle treatment.

B

The correlation between JUND and negative ferroptosis regulator in CGGA

	R value in grade IV primary glioma	P value	R value in grade IV recurrent glioma	P value
AIFM2	0.034	7.6E-01	0.252	2.35E-01
AKR1C1	0.076	4.93E-01	-0.137	5.24E-01
CBS	0.299	5.77E-03	0.156	4.67E-01
CD44	-0.113	3.08E-01	-0.027	8.99E-01
CISD1	-0.233	3.33E-02	-0.383	6.45E-02
DHODH	0.097	3.81E-01	0.035	8.72E-01
FDF1	0.032	7.7E-01	-0.224	2.93E-01
FTH1	0.105	3.44E-01	0.114	5.95E-01
GCH1	-0.032	7.72E-01	-0.09	6.75E-01
GCLC	-0.307	4.57E-03	-0.02	9.26E-01
GCLM	-0.239	2.89E-02	-0.31	1.4E-01
GPX4	0.58	7.15E-09	0.673	3.09E-04
GSS	0.204	6.21E-02	0.314	1.35E-01
HMGCR	-0.225	3.97E-02	-0.356	8.78E-02
HSPB1	0.182	9.85E-02	0.373	7.27E-02
MT1G	-0.145	1.89E-01	-0.325	1.21E-01
NFE2L2	-0.527	2.58E-07	-0.166	4.39E-01
SLC7A11	-0.192	8.07E-02	-0.222	2.97E-01
TRIT1	0.17	1.22E-01	0.127	5.55E-01
TXNRD1	-0.313	3.77E-03	-0.173	4.18E-01

C

JUND vs GPX4 in Ivy Glioblastoma

	R value	P value
CTpzn	0.135	0.511
CTpan	0.121	0.457
CThbv	0.252	0.258
CTmvp	0.150	0.446
CT	0.107	0.265
IT	0.076	0.724
LE	0.154	0.530
CTpzn + CTpan	0.093	0.460

Figure 2. JunD is correlated with GPX4 in RNA-seq datasets. (A) Bar plot of the gene expression correlations between JunD and negative ferroptosis regulator in CGGA mRNA-seq_325 dataset. R-values of primary and recurrent glioblastoma are shown. **(B)** R-values and p-values of the gene expression correlations between JunD and negative ferroptosis regulator in CGGA mRNA-seq_325 dataset. **(C)** R-values and p-values of the gene expression correlations between JunD and GPX4 across different anatomic positions in Ivy Glioblastoma Atlas Project. CT: cellular tumour; CTpzn: peri-necrotic zone in CT; CTpan: pseudopalisading cells around necrosis in CT; CThbv: hyperplastic blood vessels in CT; CTmvp: microvascular proliferation in CT; IT: infiltrating tumour; LE: leading edge

A

Figure 3. Promoter region analysis of GPX4 predicts JunD motifs. (A) Transcription factors binding sites prediction using Eukaryotic Promoter Database. The region between -2000 ~ +100 base pairs concerning the GPX4 starting site has been analysed with a cut-off p-value of 0.0001. Two binding sites for JunD motifs (-1486, -856) have been predicted. **(B)** Verification of transcription factor binding sites with real-world Chip-seq data using ChIPSummitDB. The region between -2000 ~ +100 base pairs concerning the GPX4 starting site has been analysed (highlighted in yellow). 14 JunD Chip-seq antibodies have been predicted by the overlap between JunD Chip-seq antibody recognition sites and the JunD motif binding site.

7. Reference

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